

**“ASSESSMENT OF PRESCRIPTION PATTERN IN PAEDIATRIC PARTICIPANTS
WITH ACUTE RESPIRATORY TRACT INFECTIONS (ARTI) AT A TERTIARY
CARE HOSPITAL”**

Antonita A¹, Monisha B², Divya Priya N³, Ilanchezhian K⁴, Mandara M.S^{5*}

^{1,2,3,4,5} Department of Pharmacy Practice, KLE College of Pharmacy, Rajajinagar, Bengaluru-560010. KLE Academy of Higher Education and Research, Belagavi-590010, Karnataka, INDIA

***Correspondence Author:**

Mandara M S

Department of Pharmacy Practice, KLE College of Pharmacy, Rajajinagar, Bengaluru-560010. KLE Academy of Higher Education and Research, Belagavi-590010, Karnataka, INDIA

ABSTRACT

Background:

Acute respiratory tract infection (ARTI) is defined as respiratory symptoms which lasts for the period less than 21 days. On average there will be 3-6 episodes of ARTI annually observed in children below 5 years. National institute for health care excellence produce guidelines and recommendations to improve evidence-based health outcome in achieving rational therapy. On evaluation of prescription pattern according to WHO drug utilization 1997 we can reduce the adverse drug reaction and enhance the rationality of the treatment for appropriate indication.

Objective:

Primary Objective: To assess the rationality of prescription pattern in acute respiratory tract infection using NICE guidelines.

Secondary Objective: To analyse the prescription of ARTI according to WHO Indicators and Lexicomp database

Method:

The proposed prospective observational study was carried out in 120 participants admitted in a tertiary care hospital at Bengaluru for a period of 6 months.

Result: A Total of 120 participants were included in the study, out of which males were commonly affected i.e. (66.66%) compared to females (33.33%).

Among all LRTI (25%) and Pneumonia (20.83%) were frequently encountered infections. The study states that 82.4% of prescriptions adhere to NICE Guidelines and 63.59% follow Essential drug medicine list. The commonly prescribed antibiotics were Ceftriaxone (67.02%) and Azithromycin (25.53%)

Conclusion: The data was collected to identify the rationality of the prescription. The present study indicates the need for screening prescription of Acute respiratory tract infection in paediatric population for rationality, monitoring of these participants by using NICE guidelines, Essential medicine list, WHO prescribing indicators and Lexicomp database

Key words: Acute Respiratory Tract Infections, WHO Prescribing indicators, Essential Medicine List, NICE Guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Acute respiratory tract infection is defined as the respiratory symptoms which last for the period less than 3 weeks. On an average there will be 4-7 episodes of ARTI per year seen in children below 5 years. Among all the bacteria groups streptococci, takes the lead to cause this ARTI. Even Corynebacterium diphtheria and N Meningitis are also involved in causing such illness. Staphylococcus aureus and Pneumococcus superimpose the affected infection to cause further complications like ear sinuses, and mastoids. Hence, prior vaccination is very necessary to decline the incidence of ARTI.^[1]

Infants and children are the most susceptible population to get infected to such illnesses. ARTI is the major leading cause of death in the paediatric population. Epidemiologically 1.9 million children die per year in developing countries and 20% of deaths are seen in India.^[2]

Especially children under 6 years of age were found to be at higher risk of getting LRTI. Under them, paediatrics of prematurity predicts to have severe viral LRTI. The reason behind the mortality in these children was found to be insufficient breastfeeding by the mother.^[3]

Since the lung is the most vulnerable organ to cause ARTI compared to any other, the amount of pathogen present in the air is higher which increases the risk to cause such infection and inflammation. Around 11,000-15,000 1 of inhaled air contains pathogens, pollutants, and allergens. Suppose if these microbes enter, they are trapped in the mucus layer coating of nasal epithelium causing upper respiratory tract infection, if still these microbes travel, they reach the pharynx with the help of ciliary motion leading to inflammation.^[4]

On Evaluation of prescription pattern according to WHO Drug Utilization 1997 we can reduce the adverse reaction and enhance the rationality of treatment for appropriate indication [5]

According to Danish international recommendation, a patient suspected of pneumonia is treated with antibiotics, contrary acute bronchitis cannot be treated with antibiotics. However, pneumonia is difficult to differentiate from other LRTIs with only symptoms. Hence few tests like the Point of Care Test (POCT) and the C-Reactive Protein test (CRP) are used. The advantage of CRP testing is that it can reduce antibiotic prescribing in prescription. Since CRP testing is non-specific markers a chest X-ray is also used as a diagnosing criterion to confirm it is pneumonia [6]

In 1996 multiplex reverse RT-PCR was developed to identify 9-19 non-colonizing ARI Pathogens. This was initially used in the German paediatric infection network on ARI pathogens. Here the goal of the study was to identify whether the occurrence of ARI is due to climatic factors and epidemics among children can also be identified.[7]

Prescribers should possess important skills before prescribing the medications to the patients. The prescribed drug should be therapeutically useful with low-cost management. Before prescribing he/she should know about both the drug and disease. Specifically, should possess knowledge of pathophysiology, pharmacology, and microbiology. In many systemic reviews, it was proved that prescription errors occur from 4.2% to 82% due to prescribing errors.

Frequent analysis of prescriptions may not analyse the prescription pattern but it can help doctors to upgrade themselves to enhance the rationality of the prescription. If paediatrics are considered the pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, and psychological variations are seen compared to the adult population. Hence skills to prescribe is very mandatory.[8]

Recent guidelines from the UK Department of Health's standing medical advisory committee underscore the importance of shifting away from viewing antibiotics as the primary solution for relieving symptoms of respiratory tract infections. Instead, the emphasis is on adopting a "NO or DELAYED ANTIBIOTICS" prescribing approach for most patients. To effectively implement this change, it's crucial for both patients and healthcare providers to develop proper knowledge, skills, and strategies regarding prescription behaviour at the parental level.[9]

Over the past two decades, there hasn't been any introduction of new antibiotics specifically designed to treat acute respiratory tract infections. Concurrently, there's been a concerning rise in antibiotic resistance among bacterial pathogens. Consequently, it's imperative to minimize antibiotic exposure in the paediatric population to better preserve the efficacy of existing antimicrobial medications and enhance stewardship efforts.^[10]

It is necessary to conduct a prescription audit, the core of WHO Indicators helps to improve prescribing patterns and promote the rationality of drugs.

The WHO Prescribing Indicators:

1. Avg. no. of medications per prescription encountered
2. Percentage of medications prescribed by generic name
3. Percentage of prescriptions encountered with antibiotics
4. Percentage of prescriptions encounters with injections
5. Percentage of medications prescribed from the Essential - Drug List (EDL) or formulary.^[11]

According to a longitudinal population-based cohort study, factors such as age, gender, birth characteristics, ethnicity, breastfeeding, socioeconomic status, and housing conditions contribute to acute respiratory tract infections in children aged 0-2 years in West Greenland.^[12]

It is a burden to differentiate individual respiratory infections caused by a virus in the paediatric age group. The study shows that a molecular-based study was performed and reported >21% of ARTIs in the Paediatric department of the Netherlands, where the cause is seasonal influenza in the winter season and annual hospitalization exceeds 1.5 per 100 children less than 3 years old. The main viral pathogen found here is rhinovirus. Many HRV molecular diagnoses are hampered in interpreting the virus.^[13]

Respiratory tract infections remain a significant concern in paediatric healthcare globally, particularly regarding airway-related conditions. The burden of this disease is due to:

1. High incidence
2. Substantial morbidity
3. Tendency to over diagnose
4. Overuse/ misuse of antibiotic

Relevant contributor to health care cost.^[14]

Sometimes children could be exposed to cigarette smoke even through intrauterine form. If a mother smokes during pregnancy higher risk can be seen in low birth length and low birth weight of the baby. Passive exposure to smoke can cause asthma and broncho hyper-responsiveness.^[15]

Recent studies in Africa and North America conducted widespread routine vaccination against encapsulated bacteria, showing that most respiratory diseases are due to viral infections predominantly (RSV, HRV). The Pneumonia etiology research study on children's health compared more than 4000 population admitted with CAP with more than 5000 community control in seven countries including sub-Saharan, Africa, and Southeast Asia and it is a contrast to the prior findings, it shows that RSV is the larger etiological fraction (31%) compared to all other studied pathogens. Both RSV and Influenza virus are leading causes in Europe.

According to the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, Pneumococcal Conjugate Vaccines (PCVs) have been introduced in all the children's vaccination schedules. However, the Influenza vaccine is only a part of the vaccination schedule in children with greater risk. PREPARE (Platform for European Preparation against (RE)- Emerging Epidemics) is a large-scale European commission-funded network working on a clinical research study on respiratory infection studies. The Multicentre European study of Major infection disease syndrome (MERMAIDS) is a part of PREPARE platform studies on findings of etiology and management of ARIs.^[16]

Acute Respiratory infections place a major cost burden on families and health care services hence WHO has recently received Pneumonia managing guidelines stating only severe pneumonia requires hospitalization and antibiotic use. Even though various studies demonstrate guidelines Vietnam failed to adopt, where even mild conditions of pneumonia were hospitalized and treated with antibiotics. Asia acted as the epicentre for antimicrobial resistance amplification given to ease the access and frequency of antibiotics in Asian countries including Vietnam. By the implementation/ amplification health service cost burdens were reduced, inappropriate use of antibiotics was reduced, and morbidities were declined.^[17]

Thereby, this study is conducted to observe the physician prescription pattern to determine practices related to ARTI management and to provide recommendations to enhance their practices in tertiary care hospitals.^[18]

NEED FOR THE STUDY

- Irrational drug prescription leads to ineffective treatment, occurrence of adverse effects, prolonged duration of illness and suffering to patient and increased economic burden to society
- Since children are more vulnerable than adults, it is crucial that principles of rational prescription are strictly adhered to standard guidelines
- Pediatric study is challenging due to small sample size, but it is necessary to achieve more efficient and effective preventive care
- A prevalent issue in pediatric therapeutics is the insufficient availability of age-appropriate pharmaceutical products, highlighting the crucial need for enhanced and safer drug delivery methods for this population.

AIM

To assess the prescription pattern of paediatric participants with acute respiratory tract infection using standard treatment (NICE Guidelines) and essential medicine lists.

OBJECTIVES

PRIMARY OBJECTIVE:

- To assess the rationality of prescribing patterns in acute respiratory tract infection using NICE Guidelines and Essential Medicine List

SECONDARY OBJECTIVE:

- To analyze the prescription of acute respiratory tract infection according to WHO prescribing indicators
- To identify potential drug-drug interactions in paediatric participants suffering from acute respiratory tract infections
-

METHODOLOGY

STUDY DESIGN:

Prospective observational study

STUDY SITE:

The proposed study was conducted in Paediatric In-Patient at a tertiary care hospital, Bengaluru, Karnataka.

STUDY DURATION:

The duration of the study was 6 months

SAMPLE SIZE:

From the calculation, the sample size was 120

STUDY CRITERIA**INCLUSION CRITERIA:**

- Paediatric participants below 18 years suffering from acute respiratory tract infections
- All paediatric inpatients and ICU paediatric participants diagnosed with Acute respiratory tract infections (ARTI)
- Parents/ Legal guardians of the subjects who are willing to sign the written informed consent and assent of the child above 8 years who are willing to participate in the study

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Paediatric participants admitted to the Department of Emergency Medicine and paediatric subjects suffering from psychiatric conditions are excluded
- Participants of other co-morbidities are excluded

STUDY PROCEDURE

STEP 1 -The research was conducted in the department of paediatrics after obtaining approval from the Institutional Human Ethical Committee, KLE College of Pharmacy, Bengaluru

STEP 2 -The subject who met the study criteria was enrolled in the study by obtaining the signed written informed assent and consent form.

STEP 3 -The data such as demographics, chief complaints, past medical and medication history, laboratory reports, and medication data were documented in case record form

STEP 4 -The collected prescription data was assessed to identify the rationality of the prescription pattern using standard treatment (NICE Guidelines) and Essential Medicine List (EML)

STEP 5 -The prescription details were used to analyse the prescription according to WHO indicators and to identify potential drug-drug interactions by using the Lexicomp database

STEP 6 -The obtained data was subjected to the statistical analysis to get the result

RESULTS

1. AGE AND GENDER

As per the study sample size, 120 patients were enrolled. Out of which 80/120 were male (66.66%) and 40/120 were female (33.33%). Males are prone when compared to females in the study population. Patients enrolled ranges from the day of birth to 18 years of age. The mean age and standard deviation were found to be 3.26 ± 2.804 . Maximum number of subjects prone to ARTI were within the age group of 0-1 years of age. The presenting signs and symptoms observed initially were cough, fever, breathlessness, respiratory distress, sore throat.

Table 1: Gender wise distribution of the subjects suffering from ARTI:

SL.No.	Gender	Percentage
1	Male	66.63%
2	Female	33.36%

Figure 1: Pie chart representation of gender distribution of subjects.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of age.

PARAMETER	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION
Age	3.26	2.804

Figure 2: Bar chart representation of age-wise distribution

2. INFECTIOUS CONDITION

Out of 120 participants, the subjects were diagnosed with Lower respiratory tract infections (LRTI) in 30/120 subjects (25%), Acute pneumonia in 25/120 subjects (20.83%), Bronchiolitis in 16/120 subjects (13.33%), WALRI in 14/120 subjects (11.66%), Respiratory distress in 9/120 subjects (7.5%), Acute exacerbation of wheeze in 9/120 subjects (7.5%), Acute pharyngitis in 7/120 subjects (5.83%), Acute tonsillitis in 4/120 subjects (3.3%), Croup in 4/120 subjects (3.3%), Laryngitis in 2/120 subjects (1.66%).

LRTI was the most frequent condition observed in subjects followed by Pneumonia, Bronchiolitis, WALRI and Respiratory distress.

Table 3: Distribution of infections encountered.

INFECTIONS ENCOUNTERED	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
LRTI	30	25%
Pneumonia	25	20.83%
Bronchiolitis	16	13.33%
WALRI	14	11.66%
Acute exacerbation of wheeze	9	7.5%
Respiratory distress	9	7.5%
Pharyngitis	7	5.83%
Tonsillitis	4	3.3%
Croup	4	3.3%
Laryngitis	2	1.66%

Figure 3: Pie-chart representation of distribution of infections encountered in ARTI.

Table 4: Prescription pattern of drugs according to NICE Guidelines.

Drugs	According to NICE Guidelines	Frequency	Percentage
Neb. Levosalbutamol	YES	78	65%
Inj. Pantoprazole	NO	76	63.33%
Inj. Paracetamol	YES	70	58.33%
Inj. Ceftriaxone	YES	63	67.02%
Neb. Budesonide	YES	57	47.50%
Inj. Ondansetron	YES	37	30.83%
Saline nasal drops	YES	34	28.33%
Syp. Oseltamivir	YES	29	24.16%
Syp. Azithromycin	YES	24	25.53%
Neb. Ipratropium bromide+ Levosalbutamol	YES	22	18.33%
Inj. Amoxicillin + Clavulanate	YES	21	22.34%
Inj. Methylprednisolone	YES	20	16.66%
Syp. Ambroxol	NO	18	15%
Syp. Cetirizine	YES	16	13.33%
Tab. Lansoprazole	YES	9	7.50%
Tab. Montelukast	YES	7	5.83%

Figure 4: Bar graph representation of drugs prescribed in our study**Table 5: Prescription pattern of drugs according to Essential Medicine List (EML)**

Drugs	According to EML	Administered
Neb. Levosalbutamol	YES	78
Inj. Pantoprazole	NO	76
Inj. Paracetamol	YES	70
Inj. Ceftriaxone	YES	63
Neb. Budesonide	YES	57
Inj. Ondansetron	YES	37
Saline nasal drops	NO	34
Syp. Oseltamivir	NO	29
Syp. Azithromycin	YES	24
Neb. Ipratropium bromide+ Levosalbutamol	YES	22
Inj. Amoxicillin + Clavulanate	YES	21
Inj. Methylprednisolone	YES	20
Syp. Ambroxol	NO	18
Syp. Cetirizine	YES	16

Tab. Lansoprazole	NO	9
Tab. Montelukast	NO	7

Figure 5: Bar graph representation of count of drugs present in EML

The study states that 82.41% prescription pattern is adhered to NICE Guidelines. The deviation from NICE guidelines was found to be 17.6%. The percentage of drugs prescribed as per Essential Medicine List was found to be 63.59%.

4. DISTRIBUTION OF DRUGS PRESCRIBED

The most commonly prescribed drug in the study was Antibiotics which was prescribed in 94/120 prescriptions (78.33%). Ceftriaxone (67.02%) and Azithromycin (25.53%) were commonly prescribed antibiotics followed by Amoxicillin+ Clavulanate (22.53%).

Bronchodilator was prescribed in 80/120 prescriptions (66.66%), Antipyretics was prescribed in 65/120 prescriptions (54.16%), Corticosteroids was prescribed in 59/120 prescriptions (49.16%), Anti-histamines was prescribed in 25/120 prescriptions (20.83%).

Table 6: Distribution of commonly prescribed drugs:

DRUGS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
ANTIBIOTICS	94	78.33%
BRONCHODILATORS	80	66.66%
ANTI-PYRETICS	65	54.16%
CORTICOSTEROIDS	59	49.16%
ANTI-HISTAMINE	25	20.83%

Figure 6: Bar graph representation on percentage of commonly prescribed drugs

5. WHO PRESCRIBING INDICATORS

Table 7: The WHO prescribing indicators are:

SL. No	WHO prescribing indicators	Value
1	Average number of drugs per encounter	8.61
2	Number of drugs prescribed by generic name	1.8
3	Percentage of encounters with an antibiotic prescribed	24.69%
4	Percentage of encounters with an injection prescribed	38.15%
5	Percentage of drugs prescribed from the Essential Drugs List (EDL) or formulary	63.59%

6. DRUG INTERACTIONS

Drug-drug interactions found among participants were 19/120 prescription (15.83%), Out of which 2/19 interaction was major (1.8%) and 17/19 interactions were of moderate severity (14.16%)

Table 8: Distribution of potential drug-drug interactions in ARTI

Drug- drug interactions found among participants (%)	Major interaction found (%)	Moderate interaction found (%)
15.83%	1.8%	14.16%

Figure 7: Bar chart representation of distribution of potential drug- drug interactions found.

MAJOR SEVERITY:

Table 9: Distribution of drugs with major severity:

INTERACTING DRUGS	FREQUENCY	INTERVENTION
Inj. Ketamine [2-3hrs] + Inj. Tramadol [5-6hrs]	1	CNS depressants may enhance the CNS depressant effect of opioid agonist. Avoid concomitant use of opioid agonist or CNS depressant when possible. This combination should be used only when alternative treatment options are inadequate. If combined, limit the dosage and duration of each drug to the minimum possible.
Inj. Amikacin [2-3hrs] + Inj. Colistimethate [1-3hrs]	1	Aminoglycoside may enhance the nephrotoxic and neuromuscular-blocking effect of colistimethate. Due to potential additive or synergistic toxicities between colistimethate and aminoglycoside antibiotics, this combination should be avoided whenever possible. If use is necessary, renal and neuromuscular function of the patient should be closely monitored.

MODERATE SEVERITY:**Table 10: Distribution of drugs with moderate severity:**

INTERACTING DRUGS	FREQUENCY	INTERVENTION
Inj. Amikacin [2-3hrs] + Inj. Ceftazidime [1-2hrs]	1	Cephalosporins may enhance the nephrotoxic effect and decrease the serum concentration of aminoglycosides. Close monitoring of nephrotoxicity in patients receiving both aminoglycoside and cephalosporin.
Inj. Amikacin [2-3hrs] + Inj. Piperacillin and tazobactam [1-1.5hrs]	1	Penicillin may decrease the serum concentration of aminoglycosides. Closely monitor aminoglycoside levels in patients receiving penicillin.
Inj. Linezolid [5-6hrs] + Inj. Ondansetron [3-4hrs]	1	Ondansetron may enhance the serotonergic effect of serotonergic agents which could result in serotonin syndrome (e.g.: hyperreflexia, clonus, hyperthermia, tremor, autonomic instability, diaphoresis) when these drugs are combined. Reduce the drug concentration/ doses when such combinations are required.
Inj. Cetirizine [8.3hrs] + Inj. Magnesium sulphate [4hrs]	1	Magnesium sulphate may enhance the CNS depressant effect of CNS depressants. Monitor closely for enhanced CNS depression when using higher dose/ injectable magnesium sulphate along with cetirizine.
Inj. Gentamycin[2-3hrs] + Inj. Piperacillin and tazobactam [1-1.5hrs]	1	Penicillin may decrease the serum concentration of aminoglycosides. Close monitoring of aminoglycoside levels in patients receiving penicillin's is necessary.
Inj. Gentamycin [2-3hrs] + Inj. Ceftriaxone [5.8-8.7hrs]	1	Cephalosporins may enhance the nephrotoxic effect and decrease the serum concentration of aminoglycosides. Increase monitoring for evidence of nephrotoxicity in patients receiving both cephalosporin and aminoglycosides.
Syp. Azithromycin [68hrs] + Syp. Domperidone [7.4-20hrs]	3	QT prolonging agents may enhance the QTc prolonging effect of domperidone. Consider alternatives for this combination, if use is necessary monitor for QTc interval prolongation and arrhythmia.

INTERACTING DRUGS	FREQUENCY	INTERVENTION
Inj. Vecuronium [20-40min] + Inj. Clindamycin [2-3hrs]	1	Lincosamide antibiotics may enhance the neuromuscular-blocking effect of Vecuronium. Monitor for prolonged/enhanced neuromuscular blockade during concomitant use of these agents.
Neb. Levosalbutamol [3-6hrs] + Neb. Budesonide[2-4hr] and formoterol [9-12hr]	2	Coadministration of sympathomimetics may enhance the ADR of sympathomimetics. Closely monitor for increased sympathomimetic effects (Heart rate, BP) during concomitant use.
Neb. Levosalbutamol [3-6hrs] + Neb. Salmeterol [5.5hrs]	1	Sympathomimetics may enhance the ADR effect of other sympathomimetics. Close monitoring of increased sympathomimetic effects (Heart rate, BP) during concomitant use.
Syp. Chlorpheniramine, Phenylephrine [6-9hrs] + Syp. Levocetirizine [5-7hrs]	1	CNS depressant may enhance the ADR of other CNS depressants (sedation, drowsiness) Monitor for such effects when 2 or more CNS depressants is used
Syp. Domperidone [7-20hrs] + Syp. Linezolid [3-5hrs]	2	Monoamine oxidase inhibitor may enhance the toxic effect of Domperidone (headache, dizziness) and decrease therapeutic effect. Use caution if domperidone is coadministered with MOIs
Neb. Levosalbutamol [3-6hrs] + Oxymetazoline [3-7 hrs]	1	Sympathomimetics may enhance the adverse effect of other sympathomimetics. Monitor for increased Effect of sympathomimetics (BP, heart rate) during concomitant use.

7. RATIONAL USE OF DRUGS

Out of 120 prescriptions collected 81 prescriptions were rational (67.5%) and 39 prescriptions were irrational (32.5%). Deviation from rationality is mainly due to prescribing of antibiotics for viral infection is not recommended as per NICE Guidelines and potential drug- drug interactions also results in irrational prescription.

Table 11. Rational prescriptions found in our study

RATIONAL	81 prescriptions	67.5%
IRRATIONAL	39 prescriptions	32.5%

Figure 9: Bar-graph representation of distribution of rational prescriptions

DISCUSSION

Our study is a prescription-based survey to assess the prescription according to NICE guidelines and Essential Medicine List (EML) which help in promoting rational drug use.

The prescription details are used to analyse the prescription pattern according to WHO prescribing indicators and to identify drug interactions by using Lexicomp database.

Our study was a prescription based prospective observational study. A total number of 120 paediatric prescriptions were assessed suffering from ARTI, out of which 66.63% were male subjects and 33.36% were female subjects, out of which male is more prone than female. The presenting signs and symptoms observed initially were cough, fever, breathlessness, respiratory distress, sore throat. Similar findings have been observed in study carried by Sujata Jadhav et al^[1]

Our study states that, out of 120 participants, the subjects were diagnosed with Lower respiratory tract infections (LRTI) in 30/120 subjects (25%), Acute pneumonia in 25/120 subjects (20.83%), Bronchiolitis in 16/120 subjects (13.33%), WALRI in 14/120 subjects (11.66%), Respiratory distress in 9/120 subjects (7.5%), Acute exacerbation of wheeze in 9/120 subjects (7.5%), Acute pharyngitis in 7/120 subjects (5.83%), Acute tonsillitis in 4/120 subjects (3.3%), Croup in 4/120 subjects (3.3%), Laryngitis in 2/120 subjects (1.66%). LRTI was the most frequent condition observed in subjects followed by Pneumonia, Bronchiolitis, WALRI and Respiratory distress. This was observed in the study performed by Vandana Badaret al.^[2] and Mirza A. Begetal.^[10]

In our study the study states that 82.41% prescription pattern is adhered to NICE Guidelines. The deviation from NICE guidelines was found to be 17.6%. The percentage of prescribed medications adhering to the EML was found to be 63.59%. Similar findings have been observed in the study conducted by Shalini Chandra et al^[7]

In our study the most frequently prescribed medications were Antibiotics which was prescribed in 94/120 prescriptions (78.33%). Ceftriaxone (67.02%) and Azithromycin (25.53%) were commonly prescribed antibiotics followed by Amoxicillin + Clavulanate (22.53%). Bronchodilator was prescribed in 80/120 prescriptions (66.66%), Antipyretics was prescribed in 65/120 prescriptions (54.16%), Corticosteroids was prescribed in 59/120 prescriptions (49.16%), Anti-histamines was prescribed in 25/120 prescriptions (20.83%). Similar findings have been observed in the study conducted by Madhusmita Mishra et al.^[16] and Usha Joshi et al.^[19]

In our study the percentage of prescribed medicines adhering to the EML or formulary is 63.59%. These similar findings have been observed in study carried by Sujata Jadhav et al.^[11] and the percentage of antibiotic encountered in the prescriptions is 24.69% and the study carried by Usha Joshi et al.^[19]

In our study the most common symptoms were wheeze and LRTI of the age of 2 years were affected and the similar findings were observed in the study conducted by Charl Verwey et al.^[18]

In our study the Drug-drug interactions found among participants were 15.83%, Out of which 1.8% interaction was major that is between Inj. Ketamine [2-3hrs] + Inj. Tramadol [5-6hrs] and Inj. Amikacin [2-3hrs] + Inj. Colistimethate [1-3hrs] and 14.16% of interactions were of moderate severity between the Inj. Amikacin [2-3hrs] + Inj. Ceftazidime [1-2hrs], Inj. Linezolid [5-6hrs] + Inj. Ondansetron [3-4hrs], Inj. Cetirizine [8.3hrs] + Inj. Magnesium sulphate [4hrs], Inj. Gentamycin [2-3hrs] + Inj. Piperacillin and tazobactam [1-1.5hrs], Inj. Gentamycin [2-3hrs] + Inj. Ceftriaxone [5.8-8.7hrs], SYP. Azithromycin [68hrs] + SYP. Domperidone [7.4-20hrs], Inj. Vecuronium [20-40min] + Inj. Clindamycin [2-3hrs], Neb. Levosalbutamol [3-6hrs] + Neb. Budesonide [2-4hr] and formoterol [9-12hr], Neb. Levosalbutamol [3-6hrs] + Neb. Salmeterol [5.5hrs], SYP. Chlorpheniramine, Phenylephrine [6-9hrs] + SYP. Levocetirizine [5-7hrs], Syp. Domperidone [7-20hrs]. + SYP. Linezolid [3-5hrs], Neb. Levosalbutamol [3-6hrs] + Oxymetazoline [3-7hrs]

Conclusion

The study highlights the importance of WHO indicators, EML, and NICE Guidelines in reducing ARI complications and preventing their progression to chronic respiratory infections. However, it identifies poly-pharmacy as a major concern, with an average of 8.61 medications per prescription, well above the WHO indicators. This increases the risk of adverse reactions and antimicrobial resistance, potentially impacting prescription adherence. While the antibiotic prescription rate of 24.69% aligns with WHO recommendations, efforts are needed to further limit antibiotic use to <30% in light of high infectious disease rates in developing countries.

Study shows 17.6% of prescriptions were deviated from NICE Guidelines mainly due to prescribing the antibiotics for viral infection is not recommended as per NICE Guidelines and potential drug- drug interactions also result in irrational prescription.

More adherence to Essential Medicine List 63.59% is crucial as it ensures only necessary and effective medicines also helps in reducing medication errors and promote rational drug use.

Identifying Drug-Drug interactions is essential for patient safety and effective treatment. By identifying potential interactions health care professionals can prevent harmful consequences such as ADR, ineffective therapy, side effects and complications. It allows the pharmacist to adjust medication regimen, selection of alternate drugs or modify dosages and optimize therapeutic outcomes for patients.

Encouraging physicians to prescribe drugs using generic names is vital, given that only 18.57% of drugs were prescribed this way, falling short of WHO indicators. This practice promotes prescribing accuracy and clarity, reducing the risk of errors or confusion, particularly when multiple brand names exist for the same active ingredient.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost, praises and thanks to the **ALMIGHTY GOD**, for the wisdom he bestowed upon us, the strength, peace of mind and good health in order to accomplish this work successfully.

We are extremely grateful to our **parents** for their love, prayers, caring, selfless sacrifices, constant moral support and mellifluous affection which helped us to achieve success in every sphere of life and without their kind devotion this thesis would

have been a sheer dream.

We extend our grateful thanks to **Dr Rajamma A.J.**, Principal, KLE College of Pharmacy, Bangalore for her valuable support and constant encouragement.

We would like to thank our Head of the department **Dr. Mahesh N.M.** for his guidance and insights.

We also extend our sincere thanks to all our beloved **teachers** of KLE College of Pharmacy, Bengaluru

We extend our gratitude to Consultant Pediatrician **Dr. Sujatha Thyagarajan**, Aster Hospitals, Bengaluru

We are very much thankful to Clinical Pharmacologist **Dr. Nisha** without whose cooperation this dissertation would have not been possible.

REFERENCES:

1. Jadhav S, Khanwelkar C. Prescribing pattern of drugs in acute Respiratory tract infection in children aged 1 to 5 years at tertiary care Teaching hospital. Biomedical and Pharmacology Journal. 2018 Dec 25; 11(4):1903-11
2. Badar V, Parulekar V, Garate P. A prescription pattern study of Respiratory tract infections in pediatric indoor patients in a tertiary care teaching hospital prospective observational study. Asian J Pharm Clin Res. 2018; 11(7):251-4.
3. Le Roux DM, Nicol MP, Myer L, Vanker A, Stadler JA, von Delft E, Zar HJ. Lower respiratory tract infections in children in a well-vaccinated South African birth cohort: spectrum of disease and risk factors. Clinical Infectious Diseases. 2019 Oct 15; 69(9):1588-96.
4. Omkar P, Vijayalaxmi MK, Hiremath G, Vinay PD. A study on Evaluation of prescription pattern of drugs in upper respiratory tract Infections in children at a tertiary care hospital. National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy, and Pharmacology. 2022; 12 (11):1911-6
5. Hansen LS, Lykkegaard J, Thomsen JL, Hansen MP. Acute lower Respiratory tract infections: Symptoms, findings, and management in Danish general practice. European Journal of General Practice. 2020 Dec 16; 26(1):14-20.

6. du Prel JB, Puppe W, Gröndahl B, Knuf M, Weigl F, Schaaff F, Schaaff F, Schmitt HJ. Are meteorological parameters associated With Acute respiratory tract infections? *Clinical infectious diseases*. 2009 Sep 15; 49(6):861-8.
7. Chandra S, Mayank K, Shaifali I, Ranjan R. Prescription analysis based on the World Health Organization core prescribing indicators in pediatric population having respiratory tract infections. *National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. 2019 Jul 31; 9(8):784-.
8. Andrews T, Thompson M, Buckley DI, Heneghan C, Deyo R, Redmond N, Lucas PJ, Blair PS, Hay AD. Interventions to influence consulting and antibiotic use for acute respiratory tract infections in children: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *PloS one*. 2012 Jan 27;7(1): e30334.
9. Korppi M, Heikkilä P, Palmu S, Huhtala H, Csonka P. Antibiotic prescribing for children with upper respiratory tract infection: a Finnish nationwide 7-year observational study. *European Journal of Pediatrics*. 2022 Aug;181 (8):2981-90.
10. Hussain S, Yadav SS, Sawlani KK, Khattri S. Assessment of drug prescribing pattern using World Health Organization indicators in a tertiary care teaching hospital. *Indian Journal of Public Health*. 2018 Apr 1;62(2):156-8.
11. Soborg B, Koch A, Thomsen VØ, Ladefoged K, Andersson M, Wohlfahrt J, Melbye M, Andersen AB. Ongoing tuberculosis transmission to children in Greenland. *European Respiratory Journal*. 2010 Oct 1;36(4):878-84.
12. Gooskens J, van der Ploeg V, Sukhai RN, Vossen AC, Claas EC, Kroes AC. Clinical evaluation of viral acute respiratory tract infections in children presenting to the emergency department of a tertiary referral hospital in the Netherlands. *BMC paediatrics*. 2014 Dec; 14:1
13. Schaad UB. Prevention of paediatric respiratory tract infections: emphasis on the role of OM-85. *European Respiratory Review*. 2005 Dec 1;14(95):74-7.
14. Pavić I, Jurković M, Paštar Z. Risk factors for acute respiratory tract infections in children. *Collegium antropologicum*. 2012 Jul 10;36(2):539-42
15. Vasconcelos MK, Loens K, Sigfrid L, Iosifidis E, Epalza C, Donà D, Matheussen V, Papachristou S, Roilides E, Gijon M, Rojo P. Aetiology of acute respiratory infection in

preschool children requiring hospitalization in Europe—results from the PED-MERMAIDS multicentre case-control study. *BMJ open respiratory research*. 2021 Jul 1;8(1): e000887.

16. Mishra M, Tripathy R, Panda P, Das M, Kumar N. Treatment pattern in children with lower respiratory tract infection in a tertiary care hospital of eastern India. *Pediatric research and education*. 2007;5(3).

17. Shaheen MH, Siddiqui MI, Jokhdar HA, Hassan- Hussein A, Garout MA, Hafiz SM, Alshareef MM, Falemban AM, Neveen AA, Nermeen AA. Prescribing patterns for acute respiratory infections in children in primary health care centers, Makkah Al Mukarramah, Saudi Arabia. *Journal of epidemiology and global health*. 2018 Dec;8(3-4):149.

18. Verwey C, Ramocha L, Laubscher M, Baillie V, Nunes M, Gray D, Hantos Z, Dangor Z, Madhi S. Pulmonary sequelae in 2-year-old children after hospitalization for respiratory syncytial virus lower respiratory tract infection during infancy: an observational study. *BMJ Open Respiratory Research*. 2023 May 1;10(1): e001618.

19. Joshi U, Hishikar R, Agrawal S, Halwai A, Kirana L, Kurrey K. Study of drug use in outdoor pediatric patients of upper respiratory tract infections in a tertiary care hospital. *International Journal of Basic & Clinical Pharmacology*. 2015 Sep;4(5):1009-2.

20. Mishra M, Tripathy R, Panda P, Das M, Kumar N. Treatment pattern in children with lower respiratory tract infection in a tertiary care hospital of eastern India. *Pediatric research and education*. 2007;5 (3).